

Satellite-based trophic index for the integration of small and medium-sized lakes into the trophic state monitoring in Brandenburg, Germany

Zamzow, M.; Matzinger, A.; Bastin, L.

The trophic index is often used to monitor the primary production of lakes. In Brandenburg, Germany, lakes are sampled several times every three years between April and October. The trophic index is then calculated from the values for phosphorus concentration, turbidity and chlorophyll-a content. This is usually only done for lakes that are monitored according to the Water Framework Directive (area > 50 ha). The low temporal resolution in combination with natural annual variations makes trend analysis of trophic levels very difficult and a high proportion of lakes are excluded from this monitoring.

Satellite images can be used to obtain information on chlorophyll-a and turbidity. Phosphorus, as a nutrient for algae, also has an indirect effect on water color. There are already many indices based on the Copernicus Sentinel-2 program, such as the Normalized Difference Chlorophyll Index, which can be used for real-time water monitoring. In addition, annual data are essential for lake management to identify long-term trends. The trophic index is a widely used and easily interpreted indicator in this regard.

The AD4GD project explored i) which bands of the Sentinel-2 images are best suited for estimating trophic state, ii) how the data can be temporally aggregated within a season, and iii) whether one pixel within a lake is sufficient to reliably describe the trophic state of the lake. Especially the latter was necessary to apply the method to small lakes where regular monitoring is not available.

The developed Normalized Difference Trophic Index (NDTI), aggregated over the months of April to October, best represented the trophic index based on measured values. It was developed and validated using 294 lakes in Brandenburg with trophic data between 2018 and 2022 and is defined for a satellite image as

$$NDTI_{image} = \frac{B5 - B2}{B5 + B2}$$

Band 5 describes the near infrared reflectance at 705 nm, band 2 the reflectance of blue light at 490 nm. In oligotrophic lakes, band 2 reflectance usually dominates and the index is below zero. The trophic index based on in-situ measurements is best calculated from monthly values. Similarly, $NDTI_{image}$ is first averaged monthly and then seasonally (April to October in Germany).

The resulting $NDTI_{season}$ was found to be highly correlated with the in-situ data for the available years (Pearson correlation coefficient between 0.83 and 0.92). Thus, it allows a comparison of the trophic state of lakes in the Brandenburg region. The data are available at an annual resolution, which is three times more frequent than the conventional analysis. This allows a much more reliable trend analysis, which can be used to monitor the success of water quality improvement measures or to identify water quality problems more quickly. Small lakes can be included in the monitoring without much effort.

A first sensitive analysis has shown that the classification of eutrophic water bodies is more reliable than that of oligotrophic water bodies. Further factors influencing the accuracy of the method will be investigated in a subsequent sensitivity analysis.